

Multi-layer approach for product portfolio optimization: Waste to added value products.

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Abstract.

A multi-stage multilayer systematic procedure has been developed for the selection of the optimal product portfolio from waste biomass as feedstock for systems involving water-energy-food nexus. It consists of a hybrid heuristic, metric based, and optimization methodology that evaluates the economic and environmental performance of added value products from a particular raw material. The first stage preselects the promising products. Next, a superstructure optimization problem is formulated to valorize or transform waste into the optimal set of products. The methodology has been applied within the waste to power and chemicals initiative to evaluate the best use of the biomass residue from the olive oil industry towards food, chemicals and energy. The heuristic stage is based on literature review to analyze the feasible products and technologies. Next, simple metrics have been developed and used to preselect products that are promising. Finally, a superstructure optimization approach is used to design the facility that processes leaves, wood chips and olives into final products. The best technology to recover phenols from “alperujo”, a wet solid waste/byproduct of the process, consists of the use of membranes, while for the recovery of phenols from olive leaves and branches adsorption is the selected one. The investment required to process waste adds up to 110.2 million € for a 100 kt/yr of olives production facility while the profit depends on the level of integration. If the facility is attached to an olive oil production installation, the generated profit ranges between 14.5 MM €/yr (when the waste is purchased at prices of 249 € per tonne of alperujo and 6 € per tonne of olive leaves and branches) and 34.3 MM €/yr, when the waste material is acquired for free.

Keywords: Food-water-energy nexus, multiproduct facility, superstructure optimization, olive waste valorization.

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Introduction

The term water-energy-food (WEF) nexus was coined back in 2011 in the World Economic Forum to strengthen the links among different resources and to provide basic and universal rights to food, water, and energy security.¹ Since then, WEF nexus has gained increasing attention globally from different perspectives (e.g., engineering, social sciences, policy) due to their critical importance towards sustainable development. A key challenge in addressing WEF nexus is the need to consider the strong interactions among the various components. For example, zones of drought have food and energy security problems because of the high consumption of water supply involved in their production². The energy, food and water demand has increased in the world because of the rise in the population. Therefore, there is a growing need for improving the efficient use of resources within the WEF nexus. One important point to promote and strengthen the WEF nexus is to employ the circular economy approach. One example is the case of the agricultural sector, in particular the food industry, that generates a large amount of waste that can generate greenhouse gases or pollute water, due to the decomposition of the residues. If such wastes were used as raw materials to produce added value products or to generate energy, they become a valuable resource. Thus, the circular economy concept is a strategy that improves the economics and the environmental impact³ as it can be seen in previous cases in the orange⁴ and coffee⁵ industries and the production of biofuels⁶.

In the case of processing olives to produce olive oil, several wastes are produced including branches, leaves, and a wet solid lignocellulosic material called "alperujo". Recently, 19-20 million tons of olives per year have been harvested around the world. Spain is the largest producer with estimated shares ranging between 25-40% of the world's production and 41-72% of the total amount of olives produced in Europe. Greece and Italy follow Spain as major world producers representing 8-16% and 11-18%, respectively⁷. In Europe, 50-70% of the olive production is devoted to obtaining olive oil, while the rest is used to develop different types of table olives. In the case of Spain, 90-94% of the amount of olive harvesting is employed to produce olive oil⁸.

Since ancient times, olive oil and diverse types of leaves and branches have been used to produce various types of foods, medicines, perfumes, and fuels. Recently, attention has been given to the valuable

components contained in olive milling wastes including phenols, organic matter (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium), sugars, among other species. Several works have evaluated the recovery of phenols and compared alternative processing technologies for the different types of residues such as alperujo, leaves and branches. These processes can be classified mainly in two groups, namely: conventional and modern technologies. The advantages of modern technologies are a lower time of extraction, easier scale up to industrial scale, and less use of solvents among others⁹. Most of previous studies have evaluated the recovery of value-added products from an experimental point of view to determine the yield and operating conditions. In the case of membrane technology, different combinations of membranes are used to recover distinct classes of phenols. Examples of such systems include microfiltration, nanofiltration, and osmotic distillation membrane to recover phenols in general¹⁰ or the combination of microfiltration, ultrafiltration and nanofiltration membrane for the recovery of oleuropein from olive leaves and branches¹¹. Adsorption technology was employed using different types of resins and operation conditions. For instance, Yoon et al studied the adsorption of flavonoids employing the XAD-7 resin¹², while Aehlet et al. used XAD-7HP and XAD-16HP resins¹³. Bayçin et al. used a silk fibroin to recover the antioxidants, analyzing different parameters like temperatures, pH, and solid/liquid ratios¹⁴. The work of Li et al.¹⁵, evaluated eight types of resins to purify phenols and flavonoids from olive leaves. There are other studies that compare conventional and modern technologies in the recovery of phenols such as Lama-Muñoz et al. that compared the Soxhlet method to the pressurized liquid extractor¹⁶ or optimized the phenolic compound extraction through the pressurized liquid extractor changing the operating conditions¹⁷. Works by Serrano et al., presented several economic evaluation studies about different pre-treatments and recuperation of phenols after the biomethanization of the wastes¹⁸⁻²⁰. Lama-Muñoz optimized the operating conditions of pressurized liquid extraction, developing correlations to determine extraction yields, total phenols content, total flavonoids content as well as oleuropein content as a function of moisture content, temperature, and ethanol concentration²¹. Therefore, systematic methods for product selection and process design are still missing in the literature.

A systematic methodology is proposed for the selection of a set of promising products out of waste biomass to identify and select a subset and the technologies to recover them. It is applied to a particular case of study. This work aims at the development of a process for the recovery of a limited set of added-

value compounds from diverse olive oil wastes, including leaves and branches. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The second section presents the proposed methodology. Next, the general description of the formulated superstructure, associated modeling of the units, and the solution procedure for the problem are shown. Subsequently, the results are analyzed and finally, in the conclusions are drawn.

Methodology

The methodology consists of two stages. The first one deals with the pre-screening of the potential products. We define different indicators to be able to rank the high added-value products available within the biomass. Once a subset of chemicals is selected, a superstructure optimization approach is formulated to select the technologies and the optimal portfolio of products.

Products prescreening

Four different metrics are developed to quickly identify potential promising products contained or extractable from the biomass. The indicators are ranked so that first the economic potential is evaluated. Next the process conditions are evaluated. The larger the energy required to obtain a particular product, the higher is the associated operating cost. The third layer of decision making is given by the operating conditions of the process. The more extreme conditions require processing units to withstand them and increase the capital investment of the process. Finally, at the same decision level are the safety and health issues of the species involved in the processing of the waste for sustainable decisions.

Economic potential indicator

From a benefit point of view, this indicator based on the metric for inspecting sales and reactants “MISR”²² aims to identify the type of compound that is more promising from the economic perspective. This indicator is computed as the ratio between the benefit from a particular product (P), and the cost of the raw material (RM), see equation (1).

$$\eta_{profit} = \frac{m_p \cdot Cost_p}{m_{RM} Cost_{RM}} \quad (1)$$

This indicator ranks the chemicals as a function of their economic potential, where a value larger than 1 indicates economic feasibility of the product, while the greater the indicator is from 1, the more profitable the pathway is expected to be.

Energy and environmental.

a) The biomass may be converted into products. The smaller molecular size of the final product or required intermediates such as syngas requires larger energy and number of units for processing. The ratio of the molecular size of the product versus that of the raw material is representative of the energy involved as well as the equipment required. Therefore, the energy indicator, η , is computed as the ratio between the molecular weights, eq. (2):

$$\eta = \frac{MW_{RM}}{MW_{product}} \quad (2)$$

The particular case of biomass presents challenges to compute this indicator. Hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin are mostly polymers. Therefore, to estimate the molecular weight of the initial raw material the degree of polymerization by number, DP, is used.

$$MW_{RM} = DP \cdot MW_{Monomer} \quad (3)$$

Hemicellulose shows values of degree of polymerization (DP) of 100-200²³, Cellulose 700²⁴, while lignin shows a value of 60²⁵.

When dealing with lipids, the composition of the lipid as a mixture of them allows computing the average molecular weight from the distribution of fatty acids. The unit of measure is Dalton (Da=1g/mol). In some cases, the final product is already available as such within the raw material and only extraction is required. In that case this indicator becomes 1.

b) The operating conditions to process the biomass into products can also be classified by high, medium and low temperature processes such as gasification, pyrolysis and biochemical pathways. Each one of them has its own typical equipment and costs. Therefore, the maximum operating temperature and pressure across the process are also metrics to indirectly evaluate the environmental impact and safety issues of the transformation process. Operating indicators m_P , and m_T are defined as seen in equation (4).

$$\begin{aligned} m_P &= \max \{P_i\} \\ m_T &= \max \{T_i\} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The maximum temperature can also be related to the emissions since various energy sources need to be used to provide the high level of temperature. Some examples are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Temperature of typical biomass processing routes, and the sources of energy

Temperature (°C)	Process type	Source of energy	Emissions
1000	gasification	Combustion	kg CO ₂ /kg Biomass
500	Pyrolysis	Combustion / CSP	
250	High temperature Biochem	HP steam	
180	Medium temperature biochemical	MP steam	
120	Medium to low temperature biochemical	LP steam	
<100	Low temperature	LP steam/ energy integration	

c) To further distinguish among processes operating at the same temperatures and pressures, for instance, among pre-treatments in lower temperature processes, the need for adding an acid, a base or a solvent is an additional feature to characterize the process. Solvents can be flammable, explosive and /or toxic. Martínez-Gomez et al.²⁶, presented a study where the safety of a heat transfer fluid was analyzed. For quick and preliminary assessment of technologies, the processes that involved chemicals with the largest LC50 will be considered last or discarded. A safety analysis can be part of the detail process design at the superstructure optimization stage if needed.

Superstructure design

Based on the subset of promising products, a superstructure of alternatives is formulated to design the production process capable of recovering them.

Heuristic based selection of technologies

We consider different raw materials coming from the production of olive oil. On the one hand, during the harvest leaves and branches can be collected. On the other hand, once the oil is extracted from the olive, the alperujo or olive pomace is the second waste that becomes a raw material of the process. The superstructure will consider both processing lines.

Several methods to obtain olive oil are employed traditionally including pressing and centrifugation. Nowadays, centrifugation methods are more employed at industrial scale because they can work in continuous processes²⁷. Lately, two-phase and three-phase centrifugation are the more widely used. The two-phase centrifugation process uses less water and generates the least residues compared to the three-phase centrifugation process. Because of this, in Spain 90% of the production of olive oil is carried out by the two-phase method²⁸. This will be the technology of choice in this work.

The alperujo is composed of a mix of biomass and water as well as a solid fraction consisting of bones, mesocarp and skin. Alperujo has high organic content, and it presents phytotoxic components. This fact generates environmental problems, and it makes it difficult to use²⁹. One important feature of alperujo is that it is not possible to separate both phases by centrifugation, decantation, or another process from the beginning. To perform this separation it is necessary to apply a preprocessing or pre-treatment stage³⁰. The main technology is thermal pretreatment and usually consists of steam explosion and hydrothermal treatment³¹. Thermal pretreatment is necessary to solubilize the phenolic compounds in the liquid phase by means of their breakdown from complex molecules³². Next, it is possible to carry out the phase separation. In the case of industrial scale, the hydrothermal treatment is better than steam explosion because of the lower operating temperatures and pressures³⁰. Sedimentation, centrifugation, or flocculation can be employed for the separation between the liquid phase and the solid phase. At industrial scale, the best process to develop this separation is the centrifugation process due to the fast splitting, avoiding the use of chemicals such as in the case of flocculation³³. At this point, the liquid phase follows one path and the solid phase another. It should be noted that the liquid phase contains most of phenols within the alperujo. Due to this fact, the solid phase is not employed as a resource for phenols but it can be used to generate other chemicals such as biomethane¹⁸ or bioethane³⁴, power or heat³⁴, and compost³⁵. In some cases, the liquid phase can be used for irrigation. However, in this work the target is to obtain added-value compounds, the phenolic ones, due to their wide array of biological activities³⁶. Different techniques exist for the recuperation of these phenols. The first technologies, also called conventional techniques (Soxhlet and maceration), are based on the extraction of the phenols using different solvents. As a function of the compound to be obtained, one type of solvent or another is employed³³. The main problem about these techniques is the time of extraction to obtain high yields of phenols. Advanced extraction techniques allow decreasing the time of extraction and the energy consumption. These types of techniques can be classified into pressurized liquid extraction, high-pressure high-temperature, subcritical water extraction or superheated water extraction, supercritical fluid extraction, molecular distillation or short-path distillation, ultrasound-assisted extraction, microwave-assisted extraction, chromatographic methods or membrane³⁶. In this case, membranes are a good technology to perform the recovery of the phenols due to its low cost and low consumption of energy³⁷. Furthermore, this technology does not only recover the phenols but produces them

with the proper degree of purity³⁸. From the industrial point of view, there is another interesting technique to recover phenols, the adsorption techniques, or chromatographic techniques³⁹. Based on the species-pathway representation of Pham and El-Halwagi⁴⁰, Figure 1 shows the possibilities for the recovery phenols from alperujo based on the discussion presented.

Figure 1: Technologies to recovery high added-value compounds from olive pomace.

Over the last years, different technologies have been developed to extract phenols compounds from olive leaves. Maceration, Soxhlet extraction are very popular ones but the main problem is that they are difficult to scale up to industrial scale. They are used mainly at laboratory scale⁹. Other techniques such as pressurized liquid extraction, dynamic ultrasound-assisted extraction, supercritical fluid extraction, or microwave-assisted extraction have been evaluated⁴¹. Within the modern technologies, the pressurized liquid extraction process is the more promising technology for recovering polyphenols from olive leaves⁴² and it was successful from various plant matrices for phenols recovery so it can be used at industrial-scale⁴³. After applying this technique, product purification is to be implemented. Two alternatives can be used, either

membrane modules or adsorption-desorption beds. Figure 2 shows processes that can be applied to recover added value products from leaves and branches.

Figure 2: Technologies to recovery high added-value compounds from olive leaf and branches.

Superstructure definition

As referenced above, after the harvesting, cleaning, and the production of olive oil, mainly two types of wastes are generated, alperujo (the liquid waste stream from oil extraction) and hand leaves and branches. These wastes are treated separately, for the recovery of phenols. Figure 3 shows the scheme presenting the most promising technologies. The harvesting of olive and generation of olive oil is carried out for around 4 months. In this way, to develop the model of the facility, the olive leaves and branches are processed for 8 months while for 4 months the alperujo is processed. During these 4 months, the olive

leaves are dried, crushed, and stored. These treatments are necessary to avoid the degradation of olive leaves.

Figure 3: Superstructure of alternative technologies for the recovery phenols from olive pomace, olive leaves and branches and recuperation of energy.

In the case of alperujo, the first step is to carry out a hydrothermal treatment. After the pretreatment, the liquid and the solid phases are split, employing the solid phase for the generation of energy using a boiler and a steam turbine, and the liquid phase to recover phenols. The process of the recovery of phenols can be carried out through two techniques, either membranes or adsorption-desorption technologies.

In the case of leaves and branches, the first step consists of drying, milling, and storage. For the recuperation of phenols, the pressurized liquid extractor (PLE) is selected, using ethanol as green solvent. In this process, liquid and solid phases are generated. Similar to the processing of alperujo, the solid phase is employed to generate energy, and the liquid phase is employed as raw material for the recovery of phenols. To purify the phenols soluble in the solvent, either membranes or adsorption-desorption technologies are used.

The solid phase is burned to generate energy through a regenerative Rankine cycle with reheating⁴⁴.

Superstructure model formulation.

The superstructure described in the previous section, and presented in Figure 3, is modelled in this section. The modeling of the superstructure is developed unit by unit, considering mass and energy balances, thermodynamic properties, and experimental data in the appropriate unit. Surrogate models are developed from experimental data. To simplify the explanation of the superstructure, the selection of the products based on the indicator should be mentioned, for more information about this analysis, we refer to section *Results: Portfolio of products* in this work. Therefore, the phenols recovered from alperujo should be hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol while from olive leaves and branches it should be oleuropein. In addition, the explanation of the superstructure is divided into three sections for the detailed presentation of the models developed. All the units are modelled based on mass and energy balances using experimental yields from the literature as it will be explained over the following sections.

Recovery of phenols from alperujo

The composition of Alperujo depends on the olive's variety, the fruit ripeness, among others parameters, in such way it is wide variable³¹. Table 2 shows the composition of alperujo employed in this work.

Table 2: Main compound of alperujo (Adapted ^{39,45}) (WSC: Water soluble content)

Component	%Wet weight
Bones	5.062
Orujillo	17.084
WSC	0.028
Phenols	0.066
Hydroxytyrosol	0.120
Tyrosol	0.060
Oil	4.081
Water	73.500

Pre-treatment of alperujo

The first stage is the pre-treatment of the alperujo, see top line in Figure 3. The model for the pre-treatment is based on the patent number WO 2012/020159 A1. The process developed in this patent consists of one heat exchanger, a reactor, the split of bones and a centrifugation process, see Figure 3. The

first step of the pre-treatment is preheating the alperujo in a heat exchanger, using the hot stream exiting the reactor. Therefore, with this type of preheating, heat integration is achieved minimizing the consumption of steam. The preheated alperujo is sent to the reactor to carry out the pre-treatment with the steam. To provide the heating, 1.1 L of steam per kg of fed alperujo¹⁸ are used, assuming medium pressure steam at 230°C and 2.7MPa. The reactor is equipped with a stirrer and a heating jacket. In the operation, the reactor should operate around 170°C and 0.85MPa. The pretreatment increases the solubility of the organic compounds up to around 26.3% regarding the initial alperujo, and in the case of phenols, it reaches 60.4%¹⁸.

Once it has gone through the reactor, the separation of the solids and liquid phases is easier. Two types of technologies are used for such a separation, due to presence of two different particle size of the solids. A sifter is first employed to remove the bones broken in the process of crushing. Thus, two streams are generated, the bones with moisture and the rest of compounds. Generally, by the end of the process, the bones have on average 13% of moisture⁴⁶.

To perform the separation process, a centrifuge system is employed. The solid phase content is mainly orujillo, defined as the residue remaining after oil extraction from the oil, but around 25% of organic soluble compounds, or in the case of phenols 11.5% are lost in the solid phase. Besides, the content of water is around 8.7% of the product obtained⁴⁷. The liquid phase contains the majority of the organic soluble compounds as well as phenols so this stream continues the process to recovery these phenols.

To compute the cost of this pre-treatment, the data from Serrano et al. are employed, because of this type of technology is under patent. In this study, 50.000 metrics tons per year are treated, and the investment cost in the case of heat recovery reaches 330,000€, while the operation and maintenance cost for was estimated as 2% of the construction cost. Therefore, this investment cost is around $6.6 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ €/kg/yr}$ ¹⁸. Therefore, the following cost eq. (5) is used.

$$\begin{aligned} (Cost_{invest})_{PT} &= 6.6 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot m_{treat} \\ (Cost_{OM})_{PT} &= 0.02 \cdot (Cost_{invest})_{PT} \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Technologies for phenols recovery.

In this work, two technologies to recover the phenols are considered, resin adsorption columns and membrane modules, see Figure 3. Only one is to be selected.

Resin adsorption columns.

One of the most popular alternatives to recovery phenols is based on the patent WO 2013/007850 A1. This patent consists of several adsorption and desorption steps through different columns of anionic and cationic resins. The liquid phase obtained in the previous separation is fed to the columns, see the top line in Figure 3. This process is carried out by floating or force of gravity. The phenols are retained in the bed of the columns, and to desorb then, different steps are to be followed. The first step consists of the discharge of the column with water, obtaining 3,4-Dihydroxyphenylglycol and hydroxytyrosol. The second step is based on the discharge of the column with water with acid pH, obtaining hydroxytyrosol with 30-70% of purity. In the end, the column is emptied, refilled with ethyl acetate and closed. The temperature is increased with a heating jacket, then it is emptied obtaining acetate hydroxytyrosol. According to Serrano et al., the yield of this process regarding hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol, 3,4-Dihydroxyphenylglycol and Vanillic acid is about 77.8, 93.0, 75.9, 92.5 % respectively¹⁸. It should be noted that in this case, the hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol are recovered separately.

As in the previous case, this process is under patent and to compute the cost, the data of Serrano et al. are employed¹⁸. In this way, the investment cost is around 0.42 €/kg and the operation and maintenance cost 0.5€/kg/yr¹⁸ corresponding to equations (6).

$$\begin{aligned} (Cost_{invest})_{RA} &= 0.42 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot m_{treat} \\ (Cost_{OM})_{RA} &= 0.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot m_{treat} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Membranes technology.

Another alternative employed to recover phenols consists of the use of membrane modules, see the multistage membrane system to the right of Figure 3. This process is based on the purification of the olive pomace. The small area-requirement and low-energy consumption of the operation makes it popular in water treatment and feasible for olive pomace treatment⁴⁸. In this work, this technology is based on three types of membranes, two ultrafiltration membranes and one of nanofiltration membrane.

The first step of the process is to increase the pressure until the transmembrane pressure obtained achieves 0.5 bar. The yield considered for the pump is around 80%. Once it has gone through the membrane, the permeate is sent to the next membrane with another pump. In the second step with the other

pump, the transmembrane pressure (ΔP) must reach 9 bar. The final step consists of the recovery of phenols with the nanofiltration membrane. The permeate obtained in the second membrane is sent to the nanofiltration membrane with the third pump, achieving 12 bar in the transmembrane pressure. Regarding parameters employed to develop the mass balance like yields, permeate flux, transmembrane pressure, and water permeability are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Properties of membranes ⁴⁹

	J_p ($l/m^2 \cdot h$)	K_{water} ($l/m^2 \cdot bar$)	$\eta_{Phenols}$ (%)	η_{SCO} (%)
UF 1	12	218.07	21	33.7
UF 2	150	22.47	17.6	72.1
NF	13.75	5.95	100	96.4

The temperature of operation employed in the process is the ambient temperature. It should be kept in mind that membrane technology does not recover phenols separately, but a mix of phenols where the principal phenols are hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol.

In the case of membrane technology, three types of membranes are employed, two ultrafiltration membranes and one nanofiltration membrane. In the case of ultrafiltration membranes, the investment cost accounts for 5.37€/m³ per year, while operating costs take a value of 0.54€/m³ per year. The process to compute the nanofiltration membrane is the same as in the previous case, therefore investment costs are 3.79€/m³ and operating costs are 0.49€/m³/yr⁵⁰.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (Cost_{invest})_{UF} &= 5.37 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot m_{treat} \\
 (Cost_{OM})_{UF} &= 5.4 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot m_{treat} \\
 (Cost_{invest})_{NF} &= 3.79 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot m_{treat} \\
 (Cost_{OM})_{NF} &= 4.9 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot m_{treat}
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Recovery of phenols from leaves and branches.

During the harvesting of olives, around 5% by weight of olive leaves, with respect to olives, are recollected too³¹. In this point, different treatments are described to the recovery of phenols from the olive leaves and branches. As mentioned above, the main phenol content in the olive leaves is the oleuropein.

The typical composition of the olive leaves that is employed in the model is shown in Table 4. The added value products will be extracted from the carbohydrate and crude fiber. The second line of processes in Figure 3 show the processing of leaves and branches.

Table 4: Composition of olive leaves ⁵¹

Component	Amount (g/100 g olive leaves)
Protein	5.45
Oil	6.54
Carbohydrate	27.57
Crude fiber	7
Ash	3.61
Water	49.83

Drying of olive leaves

After cleaning the olives and removing the olive leaves and branches, these are dried with hot air. This technique has a crucial role in the process, because if the operating conditions are not optimal or appropriate, a big loss of total phenols content will occur. To model the process and minimize losses of total phenols the optimal operating conditions determined in the research of Erbay et al.⁵¹ are employed. In this way, to obtain the moisture content below 6%, the dryer must operate at 53.43°C⁵¹. In the model, it is assumed that the olive leaves temperature is constant across the dryer, the air temperature can decrease 3°C. Thus, it is possible to compute the airflow necessary to dry the olive leaves. The energy balance developed in the process of drying is presented below.

$$G \cdot H_{G_{IN}} + L \cdot H_{L_{IN}} = G \cdot H_{G_{OUT}} + L \cdot H_{L_{OUT}} \quad (8)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{G_i} &= Cp_{da} (T_{G_i} - T_{ref}) + \lambda \cdot Y \\ Cp_{ad} &= 1.005 + 1.84 \cdot Y \\ H_{L_i} &= Cp_{ds} (T_{L_i} - T_{ref}) + X \cdot Cp_{water} (T_{L_i} - T_{ref}) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

To compute the heat capacity of the leaves, their composition and corresponding heat capacities are used⁵².

$$Cp_{ds} = \sum_i Cp_i \cdot x_i^w \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Cp_{protein} &= 2.0082 + 1.2089 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T - 1.3129 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot T^2 \\
Cp_{fat} &= 1.9842 + 1.4733 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T - 4.8008 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot T^2 \\
Cp_{carbohydrate} &= 1.5488 + 1.9625 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T - 5.9399 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot T^2 \\
Cp_{fiber} &= 1.8459 + 1.8306 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T - 4.6509 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot T^2 \\
Cp_{ash} &= 1.0926 + 1.8896 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T - 3.6817 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot T^2
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

According to the information collected, for this operating capacity, the investment cost of the dryer is around 15,000\$, while the operation and maintenance cost is a function of removed water in the leaves and take a value around $9.82 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M€/(kg H₂O/h)⁵³.

$$\begin{aligned}
(Cost_{invest})_{dryer} &= 15,000 \cdot \delta / 10^6 \\
(Cost_{OM})_{dryer} &= 9.82 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot m_{waterremoved}
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

After completing the drying process of the leaves, they are fed to the milling process and then the powder is stored. The cost of the crushing machine is variable between \$60,000 and \$145,500. Due to the lack of information about this specific process, to be on the safe said the larger cost is used. In the case of the operation and maintenance cost, the cost of the energy consumed according to the specifications is assumed, taking a value of around 6.3 kW per ton of olive leaves milling per hour/(t/h)⁵⁴.

$$\begin{aligned}
(Cost_{invest})_{mill} &= 145,500 \cdot \delta / 10^6 \\
(Cost_{OM})_{mill} &= 4.35 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot m_{olives}
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) for phenols recovery.

Lama-Muñoz et al.²¹ developed correlations to compute the extraction yield of soluble solids content from the liquid phase as well as the oleuropein content as a function of the temperature, moisture, and the ethanol concentration. The correlations shown in eq (14) are used to compute the extraction yield and the content of oleuropein in the olive leaves:

$$\begin{aligned}
\eta_s &= 380.99 + 146.75 \cdot T^* + 12.98 \cdot MC^* - 3.52 \cdot E^* + 11.33 \cdot T^* \cdot E^* - 17.38 \cdot MC^* \cdot E^* + 25.85 \cdot (T^*)^2 \\
m_{OC} &= 40.75 + 7.59 \cdot T^* - 5.79 \cdot MC^* - 5.22 \cdot T^* \cdot MC^* - 6.14 \cdot (T^*)^2 + 10.13 \cdot (MC^*)^2
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Parameters T*, MC* and E* take values between -1 and 1. To apply these values and boundaries in the model, a variable change is presented for the moisture content, temperature and ratio between ethanol

and water added in the process. Boundaries to apply these correlations, correspond to 60-80% of ethanol, 70-190°C, and 4.70-22.60% moisture content as given in eq. (15):

$$\begin{aligned} MC^* &= 0.10 \cdot MC (4.70 - 22.60\%) - 1.5 \\ T^* &= 0.0167 \cdot T (70 - 190^\circ C) - 2.167 \\ E^* &= 0.10 \cdot E (60 - 80\%) - 7 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

In the case of this technology, the ratio between the solvent and the olive leaves should be around 7 and it is lower than the other technologies³⁰. The losses of solvent in the process are considered to be around of 2% of the solvent fed.

Based on the work of Osorio-Tobón et al, a surrogate model is developed to calculate the investment cost of the pressurized liquid extractor, given by equation (16)⁵⁵.

$$(Cost_{invest})_{PLE} = 0.2833 \cdot (V_{leaves})^2 + 0.4392 \cdot V_{leaves} + 0.0285 \quad (16)$$

Regarding the maximum range of extraction time and number of cycles in the process is 5 min and 1 cycle²¹. To obtain a continuous process, two extractors are used. While one extractor is operating the other one is cleaned and refilled with leaves powder. Taking into account these considerations, the extractor capacity is computed through equation (17).

$$V_{leaves} = \frac{(m_{leaves}) \cdot t_{extraction} \cdot n_{cycle}}{\rho_{leaves}} \quad (17)$$

The density of powdered olive leaves is considered around 1510 kg/m³⁵⁶.

The operation and maintenance cost is computed as a function of ethanol losses by the process, considering the cost of the ethanol around 0.42€/kg⁵⁷.

Purification of oleuropein content.

Two methods to purify the oleuropein have been used, membranes modules¹¹ and adsorption resins⁵⁸. Only one is to be selected.

Membrane modules.

The technology of membrane employed in the model consists of two membrane modules, to the right in the bottom of Figure 3. First an ultrafiltration membrane and next a nanofiltration membrane. The treatment of membrane to purify of oleuropein is similar to the previous case with the alperujo.

The first step is to increase the pressure with a pump until the transmembrane pressure (ΔP) generated reaches 1 bar. Having reached that pressure, the solution is sent to the ultrafiltration membrane, whose characteristics are shown in Table 5. The permeate obtained in the membrane of ultrafiltration is sent through another pump towards the membrane of nanofiltration. In this pump, the transmembrane pressure must reach 9 bar. The soluble obtained consist of other phenols, flavonoids, and carbohydrates. The process to compute the investment cost and the operation and maintenance cost uses the same equations as in the previous case.

Table 5: Properties of membranes ¹¹

	J_p (l/m ² ·h)	$\eta_{oleuropein}$ (%)	$\eta_{soluble}$ (%)
Ultrafiltration Membrane	27.5	32.81	37
Nanofiltration membrane	50	100	95

Selective adsorption of oleuropein.

The extract obtained in the pressurized liquid extraction process is filtrated through a filter under pressure to recover the ethanol, see units to the bottom left corner of Figure 3. Thus, the ethanol is collected, and recycled to the previous step. The ethanol losses are considered to be around 1%. The extract without ethanol is diluted with water, generating a ratio of grams of extract per litter of water around 100. After the adsorption process is completed, the resins are washed with distilled water and the desorption process starts. To carry out the desorption process, a 40% ethanol in water mix ⁵⁸ is added to the resins, promoting the desorption of oleuropein. To remove the water, the extracted obtained is percolated in a filter of 0.45 μ m^{15,58}. The type of resin employed is Amberlite XAD-7HP, recommended by Şahin et al. for the recovery of oleuropein from olive leaves⁵⁸. Table 6 shows the main characteristics of the resin employed in the process.

Table 6: Properties of Amberlite XAD 7 HP resin

		References
Qe (mg /g resin)	97.9	⁵⁸
ρ (g/ml)	1.05	⁵⁹
Price (€/kg)	5.00	⁵⁹

The yield of oleuropein recovery in the process of adsorption is 91%, while the process of desorption is 97%. The adsorption process runs for 180 minutes, whose adsorption capacity corresponds to 97.90 mg of oleuropein per g of resin⁵⁸ and 17.50 mg per g of resin for the rest of phenols. The adsorption

capacity is used to compute the amount of resin that it is necessary for the operation of the process, equation (18).

$$m_{resin} = \frac{m_{OA}}{Q_e} \quad (18)$$

To compute the cost of the process, the filter under pressure and the pressurized liquid extractor are considered. The filter under pressure is assumed to be a vessel and the cost will be estimated as follows⁶⁰:

$$(Cost_{invest})_{FUP} = (0.9635 \cdot (m_{steel}) + 103785) \cdot \delta / 10^6 \quad (19)$$

The weight of vessel is determined using the following equations (20)⁶¹:

$$\begin{aligned} u_t &= 0.07 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\rho_l - \rho_v}{\rho_v}} \\ D_v &= \sqrt{\frac{4V}{\pi \cdot (0.15 \cdot u_t)}} \\ L_v &= 3 \cdot D_v \\ e &= 0.023 + 0.003 \cdot D_v \\ m_{steel} &= \rho_{steel} \cdot \left[\pi \left(\left(\frac{D_v}{2} + e \right)^2 - \left(\frac{D_v}{2} \right)^2 \right) \cdot L_v + \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\left(\frac{D_v}{2} + e \right)^3 - \left(\frac{D_v}{2} \right)^3 \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The cost of the adsorption- desorption process is estimated using the price of the XAD resin and vertical vessels. The mass of resin employed in the process is determined as a function of adsorption capacity of the adsorbent and the amount of sorbent. To size the vessel, it has to be able to contain the bed of resins. An over-design factor of 10% for safety reasons and in case of bed expansion is used, eq. (21)⁶².

$$\begin{aligned} V_{vessel} &= 1.1 \cdot V_{resin} \\ D_{vessel} &= \sqrt[3]{\frac{V_{vessel}}{3 \cdot \pi}} \\ L_{vessel} &= 3 \cdot D_{vessel} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

The cost of resins XAD is considered to be 2000€/t⁵⁹ and to estimate the cost of the vessel a correlation obtained from Matche, eq (22) is used⁶⁰:

$$(Cost_{invest})_{ads} = 2 \cdot \left((0.1699 \cdot m_{steel} + 37.847) + 5 \cdot m_{resin} \right) \cdot \delta / 10^6 \quad (22)$$

The change of resin along the campaign is considered as operation and maintenance cost. One change per campaign is assumed to be on the save side.

Energy recovery

Two of the products obtained in the recovery of phenols are solid compounds made of cellulose or lignin. To improve the sustainability of the process, where the pretreatments are energy intense, the solids obtained will be employed to produce energy and generate the steam used in the pretreatment step.

The first aim is to generate the steam needed in the pretreatment stage and heat the air to the dryer; the rest of the wastes are devoted to the production of electricity. To compute the energy required to generate the steam, the type of pressure is defined. Medium pressure steam, 26 bar and 503.15 K⁶³, is produced. Therefore, based on these parameters and the amount of steam needed, that it was fixed by the characteristics of the pretreatment, the energy required is calculated using equation (23):

$$Q_{SN} = m_{steam} \cdot (Cp_{water;l} \cdot (T_{boil,water} - T_{in,water}) + \lambda_{water} + Cp_{water;g} \cdot (T_{out,steam} - T_{boil,water})) \quad (23)$$

Taking into account that the energy efficiency towards power in a Rankine cycle is around 40% (η_{SN}), the energy needed in this process is computed as in eq. (24).

$$Q_{SN,real} = \frac{Q_{SN}}{\eta_{SN}} \quad (24)$$

As previously mentioned, the sources employed to generate thermal and electrical energy are bones and orujillo whose calorific values are 4400 kcal/kg and 4100 kcal/kg, respectively⁶⁴. The efficiency of the boiler to produce thermal energy is assumed to be 80%. The analysis of the energy produced from these wastes is carried out separately, since for 4 months the alperujo is used and the rest of the year uses the olive leaves. To compute the power generated, two boilers and two turbines are modeled with the characteristics of the wastes.

The process considered to produce electricity is a regenerative Rankine cycle with reheating. This cycle is modeled unit by unit like in a previous works, considering mass and energy balance and detailed thermodynamics⁴⁴.

The cost of this section of the facility is computed through the following surrogate models⁶⁵:

$$\begin{aligned}
Cost_{turbine} &= 633000 \cdot (W_{NE})^{0.398} \\
Cost_{boiler} &= 1340000 \cdot (W_{NE})^{0.694}
\end{aligned}
\tag{25}$$

Solution procedure

Selection of technologies: Superstructure optimization

The aim of the process is the recovery of added value products together with the use of residues to produce power from the wastes of the olive oil production. Thus, the objective function is a simplified annual profit, considering life cycle of 20 years, as presented in eq. (26), where the annualized cost of the units involved allowed for the fixed costs of selecting a unit to be considered while the operating costs consider the use of utilities involved in the processing of the waste.

$$Profit_{annual} = \sum_{products} (m_{product} \cdot Cost_{product}) - \frac{1}{3} \sum_j (Cost_{invest})_j - \sum_j (Cost_{OM})_j
\tag{26}$$

Within the superstructure, the purity of the products depends on the selected technology. As a result, different prices are assigned to the products of each of the alternative path as shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Price of different phenols obtained.

	Obtained from	Price (€/kg)	Reference
Hydroxytyrosol	Adsorption	300	66
Tyrosol	Adsorption	100	67
Hydroxytyrosol/Tyrosol	Membrane	85	68
Oleuropein	Adsorption	850	69
Oleuropein	Membrane	45	70

Two operating periods are considered: the recovery phenols from alperujo operates for 4 months, while the recovery phenols from olive leaves and branches works along the rest of the year. The optimization is subjected to the models of all the units described in section “*Superstructure model formulation*” representing an NLP problem that consists of around 1818 equations and 2508 variables. The model is formulated in GAMS and solved using a multistart optimization approach with CONOPT as preferred solver. No global optimum is claimed.

Cost estimation.

After the optimization of the superstructure, the operation and maintenance costs are computed based on Sinnott and Towler’s factorial method.⁷¹ The investment cost of the facility is based on the unit’s

costs, estimated using the equations presented along the text. The total investment is estimated using lang factors for a facility that processes fluids and solids.

With regards to the production costs, the variable cost is calculated as a function of the cost of raw materials and utilities while the fixed cost is considered the cost of maintenance, operating labor, laboratory cost, supervision, plant overheads, capital charges, insurance, local taxes, and royalties. The methodology employed to develop this cost is described by Sinnott and Towler⁷¹.

Results and Discussion

As a case study for the analysis, 99,227.4 tons of olives gathered per campaign are considered. In the oil production, 800 kg of alperujo are generated per ton of olive, leaves and branches generated represent around 5% of the mass of the total amount harvested. Results obtained after the selection of products and the optimization process are shown in the next subsections.

Portfolio of products.

The first part of the results consists of the application of the indicators developed to select the product or products to obtain. In the case of study, only two indicators can be applied, on the one hand, the economic potential indicator and, on the other hand, the energy indicator regarding the rupture of the raw material in smaller parts. Regarding the indicator concerning solvents, in the majority of the processes, ethanol is employed, that is considered as a green solvent⁷². For developing the methodology, a particular composition of olive pomace and leaves and branches is taken, allowing the characterization and selection of these wastes.

Alperujo

The composition of phenols from alperujo is shown in kilograms per cubic meter in Table 8. To compute the fraction of each one in the alperujo, the density of the olive pomace density is assumed to be 1.63 g/cm^3 ⁷³. To estimate the energy indicator, it is necessary to determine the original source of the phenols. Two alternative sources are identified. We consider natural when the phenols are as such in the waste. Alternatively, they can be produced from the breakage of longer molecules. In this part of the study

only two phenols can be obtained from the different sources, they are hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol. Oleuropein, verbacoside, Hydroxytyrosol 4- β -d-Glucoside can be broken down to form hydroxytyrosol. In the case of tyrosol, it can be obtained from oleuropein and natural source. Without experimental data it is not possible to determine the proportion of rupture of each molecule. To compute the energy indicator, we assume that each source can generate the same amount. In other words, to calculate the indicator for the hydroxytyrosol, we consider 25% of each source, and in the case of tyrosol 50%. To consider the same source for the price of the products in all cases, the price at lab-scale from Sigma's web page is used, see Table 8.

Table 8: Results of indicators applied in the main phenols of alperujo.

	Amount of phenols (kg/m ³)	Amounts of phenols in alperujo (%)	Cost (€/mg)	Molecular weight (g/mol)	η_{profit}	η_{energy}	Standardization of η_{profit}
3,4-Dihydroxyphenylglycol	0.157	0.00963	10.26 ⁷⁴	170.16	1.39·10 ³	1	0.12
Hydroxytyrosol	0.540	0.03313	25.41 ⁷⁵	154.16	1.18·10 ⁴	2.652	1.00
Tyrosol	0.122	0.00748	13.1 ⁷⁶	138.16	1.62·10 ³	2.456	0.14
Vanillin	0.076	0.00466	2.45 ⁷⁷	152.15	1.60·10 ²	1	0.01
p-Coumaric acid	0.032	0.00196	6.90 ⁷⁸	164.16	1.90·10 ²	1	0.02

Table 8 shows the results of the indicators that can be applied in this case of the study. In order to rank the products, the economic potential indicator shows that the best phenols to recover are hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol, 3,4-Dihydroxyphenylglycol, p-Coumaric acid, and Vanillin, respectively. In this way, the best option for recovery is hydroxytyrosol.

Regarding the energy indicator, since the hydroxytyrosol and the tyrosol have the possibility to be obtained from other phenols, their indicator shows higher values with respect to other phenols.

In the view of results, hydroxytyrosol is the best option for recuperation but literature suggests considering both hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol.

Leaves and branches.

In the case of olive leaves and branches, the calculation procedure is the same as in the previous case, see Table 9 for the properties of the raw material. The main difference is that the composition of olive

leaves is given in dry basis. The amount of water is around 49.7% based on literature and that is the value assumed for the residue¹⁶.

Table 9: Results of indicators applied in the main phenols of olive leaves and branches.

	Amounts % (dry basis)	Amounts %	Cost (\$/mg)	Mw (g/mol)	η_{profit}	η_{energy}	Standardization of η_{profit}
Oleuropein	11.5	5.78	18.5	540.51 ⁷⁹	$1.36 \cdot 10^8$	1	1.00
Luteolin-7-glucoside	0.319	0.16	40.47	448.38 ⁸⁰	$8.28 \cdot 10^6$	1	0.06
Apigenin-7-glucoside	0.134	0.07	31.4	432.38 ⁸¹	$2.70 \cdot 10^6$	1	0.02
Verbascoside	0.086	0.04	31.45	624.59 ⁸²	$1.73 \cdot 10^6$	1	0.01
Quercetin	0.026	0.01	0.0051	302.24 ⁸³	8.49	1	0.00

In this case, it does not make sense to compute the energy indicator because all phenols are found in the waste. As a result, the compound selected for the extraction in olives leaves is the oleuropein. In this case, only one compound is selected because it is the major compound in leaves and generates the larger economic potential indicator by comparison.

Process design: selection of technologies to recover phenols.

The result of the optimization of the superstructure is presented in Figure 4. The use of membrane technology is selected to recover phenols for the case of alperujo, while for processing olive leaves and branches, the adsorption technology is the one of choice.

From the economics point of view, the recovery of phenols from alperujo should be done through the membrane technology. The main reason behind is the high cost of the resin employed to split and recover hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol separately. It should be noted that in the case of membrane technology, the product generated is a mix of phenols composed mainly by hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol, but it is cheaper compared to the use of adsorption technology and the production of both separately does not compensate the additional cost. The mix of phenols obtained through this process is around 62% of hydroxytyrosol, 26.7% of tyrosol and the rest of soluble compounds like other phenols or carbohydrates soluble. Nowadays, this type of mix of phenols has a wide use in different sectors such as pharma, food products, cosmetics, among others.

In the case of olive leaves and branches, it is more profitable to use adsorption for the recovery of phenols. Since the phenol recovered is different than from alperujo, the type of resin employed in the process must also be different, resulting in a cheaper cost. The adsorption technology allows the production of oleuropein with 85.5% purity. The quantity of phenols per month is shown in Figure 5. Note that the production of olives last 4 months, that results in the production of alperujo from processing the waste, while the rest of the year the leaves and branches are processed obtaining the oleuropein.

Figure 4: Optimal flowsheet for the processing of olive's waste. Solution of the superstructure optimization.

Figure 5: Summary of the products obtained over a year of operation from alperujo and the leaves and branches

Economic evaluation.

Using the correlations developed for each one of the units as a function of their size, the cost of each one is computed. The investment in units adds up to 18.22 M€. Table 10 shows the detail of the processing lines for alperujo and the leaves and branches. The total investment cost of the plant is around 110.23 M€.

Table 10: Investment cost of units of alperujo and olive leaves and branches.

	Treatments	Investment cost (M€)	
ALPERUJO	Pretreatment	0.524	
	Membrane Technology	0.597	
		UF 1	0.306
		UF 2	0.276
		NF 1	0.014
	Power Technology	9.919	
		Turbine	1.75
		Boiler	7.93
LEAVES AND BRANCHES	Dryer	0.01275	
	Mill	0.1455	
	Filter Under pressure	0.089	
	PLE	0.039	
	Resin Adsorption	6.319	

As shown in Table 10, the share of the alperujo pre-treatment devoted to the separation of the liquid and solid phases represents 46.74%, while the rest of the investment cost corresponds to the membrane technology. In the case of olive leaves and branches only around 3% correspond to the investment in the pretreatment. The investment cost of the turbine and the boiler take values around 1.75 and 7.93 M€ respectively. Note that the power plant represents more than half the investment in units. Note that the fact that the larger solids production comes from the alperujo results in the need to design the power island based on that production capacity.

The operation and maintenance costs are described in section “*Solution procedure*”. Typically, this methodology considers the cost of utilities like electricity and steam at the point of variable cost. But in this

case, it has not been considered due to the fact that the facility has the capacity to generate them. Two alternative solutions are presented, whether the raw materials are received a zero cost or if they are bought. In the latter case, prices of 249 € per ton of alperujo⁸⁴ and 6€ per ton of olive and branches are considered. Figure 6a shows the first alternative and Figure 6b the second one. The operation and maintenance cost without raw materials adds up to 33.75 M€/year while in the case that raw materials are considered, the costs reach a value around 53.54 M€/year. The cost increases by 61% in the case the raw materials do not belong to the facility. As Figure 6a shows, the cost of raw materials reaches 37% of the operation and maintenance cost followed by capital changes and maintenance costs. In the case of Figure 6b, costs have the same order, being the more expensive the capital changes followed by maintenance and local taxes costs.

a

b

Figure 6: Total operation and maintenance cost. a) considering raw materials; b) not considering raw materials.

Benefits from phenols correspond to around 104.7M€/year. Using eq. (26) we compute the profit, considering benefits from phenols, annualized investment cost and the operation and maintenance cost defined in Figure 6. In the case purchasing the raw materials the profit reaches 14.5 M€/year, while in the other case the profit achieved is around 34.3 M€/year. The return on investment in the case of raw materials are considered is around 16.02% while in the case of raw materials are not accounted for, it is approximately 48.61%.

Energy evaluation.

Solid wastes are used to generate energy. On the one hand, electric energy, and on the other hand thermal energy. Thermal and electrical energy requirements annual by the part of the facility to recover phenols from alperujo is around 140 kW on a monthly basis, 92.6% corresponding to thermal energy. While in the part of recovery oleuropein from olive leaves and branches achieving 60 kW monthly, 95 % corresponding to thermal energy. To better understand the operation of the facility, the thermal and electrical monthly energy requirements of alperujo and olive leaves and branches are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Energy requirement monthly. a) Alperujo thermal energy b) Alperujo electric energy c) Olive leaves and branches thermal energy d) Olive leaves and branches electric energy

Once the thermal energy requirement is fulfilled, the rest of the solid wastes are transformed into electric energy through the power plant. Results show that from the alperujo residues, 12.95 MW can be produced while from the leaves and branches the power can only be 312 kW. In view of these results, the power plant may only operate 4 months, because the rest of the months the power island of the facility should operate at such low load that will represent an issue for the units.

The electric energy consumed by the units corresponds to 10.2 kW during the alperujo treatment (4 months) and 3 kW during the leaves and branches processing (8 months), a total of 46,711 kWh, see Figure 8. Since the power plant capacity installed in the facility is around 12.95 MW and 312 kW for each of the operating periods, it is not necessary to buy this type of utilities. In this way, the facility, or the part of recovery phenols of the facility is capable to supply itself.

In the case the recovery of phenols becomes part of olive oil generation facility, the energy consumption of the main section producing the olive oil should also be analyzed. Considering the production capacity of this facility, and data from the literature, the annual energy consumed by the olive oil production is around 3,920MWh⁸⁵. Therefore, the power plant using the residue form the alperujo, with a total energy production of 37296 MWh, would be able to supply energy at this part of the facility.

Figure 8: Annual electric energy consumption by technology

Conclusions

In this work, systematic methodology has been developed for the screening and design of multiproduct facilities associated with WEF nexus. It combines hybrid heuristic-based, metric-based and superstructure optimization approaches to identify the promising high added value products so as to put together a superstructure for the design of an integrated facility that makes the most of waste and valuable products towards a sustainable biorefinery. Novel indicators have been developed to identify value-added products. The methodology has been applied to the waste from olive trees, olive leaves and branches, and alperujo from olive oil production. Value-added products of these wastes include phenols that can be used in the pharmacy, cosmetic, or food industries.

The results show that the optimal portfolio of products corresponds to the recovery of phenols, hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol from alperujo and oleuropein from olive leaves and branches, based on the economic indicator is the largest. After the selection of the products to obtain, a superstructure is formulated and optimized. As a result of the optimization, pre-treatment and membrane technology should be used from alperujo to recover of a mix of phenols while in the case of olive leaves and branches, a dryer followed by a mill, a pressurized liquid extractor, filter under pressure and resin adsorption are used. The final economic evaluation is carried out, whose profit comes to 14.5 M€ annual in the case of this process will be integrated into an olive oil production facility and 34.3 M€ annual if the raw materials have to be bought. Regarding energy, solid waste is used to generate the utilities employed in the recovery process. A power plant is integrated into the facility whose power is around 12.95 MW, which is sufficient for the recovery process.

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Nomenclature

- Cost_{boiler}: Cost of boiler (€)
- (Cost_{invest})_{ads}: Inversion cost of adsorption (M€)
- (Cost_{invest})_{dryer}: Inversion cost of dryer process (M€)
- (Cost_{invest})_{FUP}: Inversion cost of Filter under pressure (M€)
- (Cost_{invest})_{mill}: Inversion cost of mill (M€)
- (Cost_{invest})_{PLE}: Inversion cost of pressurized liquid extractor (M€)
- (Cost_{invest})_{PT}: Inversion cost of pre-treatment (M€)
- (Cost_{invest})_{RA}: Inversion cost of resin adsorption (M€)

$(Cost_{OM})_{dryer}$: Operation and maintenance cost of dryer (€)
 $(Cost_{OM})_{Mill}$: Operation and maintenance cost of mill (M€)
 $(Cost_{OM})_{PT}$: Operation and maintenance cost of pre-treatment (M€)
 $(Cost_{OM})_{RA}$: Operation and maintenance cost of resin adsorption (M€)
 $Cost_{turbine}$: Cost of turbine (€)
 Cp_{ash} : Heat capacity of ash (kJ/kg·K)
 $Cp_{carbohydrates}$: Heat capacity of carbohydrates (kJ/kg·K)
 Cp_{da} : Heat capacity of dry air (kJ/kg·K)
 Cp_{ds} : Heat capacity of dry leaves (kJ/kg·K)
 Cp_{fat} : Heat capacity of fat (kJ/kg·K)
 Cp_{fiber} : Heat capacity of fiber (kJ/kg·K)
 $Cp_{protein}$: Heat capacity of protein (kJ/kg·K)
 D_v : Diameter (m)
 D_{vessel} : Diameter (m)
 e : Thickness (m)
 E : Ethanol concentration
 E^* : Ethanol concentration (-1;1)
 G : Dry air flow (kg dry air/s)
 H_{G_i} : Enthalpy of air under “i” conditions (kJ/kg)
 H_{L_i} : Enthalpy of solid under “i” conditions (kJ/kg)
 L : Dry solid flow (kg dry leaves/s)
 L_v : Tank length (m)
 L_{vessel} : Tank length (m)
 MC : Moisture content (%)
 MC^* : Moisture content (-1:1)
 m_{leaves} : mass flow of leaves (kg/s)
 m_{resin} : mass of resin (kg)
 m_{steel} : mass of steel (kg)
 m_{steam} : mass flow of steam (kg/s)
 m_{treat} : treated mass (kg/year)
 m_i : treated mass (m³/year)
 m_{OC} : Oleuropein content (kg oleuropein/kg dry leaves)
 m_{OA} : mass of oleuropein adsorbed (kg soluble/kg dry leaves)
 m_{olives} : mass flow of olives (kg/h)
 $m_{waterremoved}$: mass flow of water removed (kg/h)
 n_{cycle} : number of cycles.
 T : temperature (°C)
 T^* : temperature (°C)
 $t_{extraction}$: extraction time (s)
 u_t : terminal velocity (m/s)
 V : steam volume (m³).
 V_{leaves} : extraction vessel capacity (m³).
 V_{resin} : Volume of resin (m³)
 V_{vessel} : Volume of vessel (m³)
 W_{NE} : net electric energy power output (MW)
 X : humidity of leaves (kg water/kg dry leaves)
 x_i^w : mass fraction of i component.
 Y : Specific moisture (kg water/kg dry air)
 δ : conversion euro dolar (0.85\$/€)
 ρ_{leaves} : Leaves density (kg/m³)
 ρ_l : Liquid density (kg/m³)
 ρ_v : Vapor density (kg/m³)
 ρ_{steel} : Steel density (kg/m³)

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TOC

Multi-layer approach for product portfolio optimization: Waste to added value products

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SYNOPSIS: Methodology and case study for the selection of added value products out of waste and process design